

ANALYTICAL STUDY ON PARENTS ATTITUDE TOWARDS THE EDUCATION OF GIRL CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO VILLUPURAM DISTRICT, TAMILNADU

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Abstract

Learning, or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, morals, beliefs, habits, and personal development, is facilitated by education. Education began as a means of passing down cultural knowledge from generation to generation. In today's world, a woman's education is critical in every way. We can only expect a happy family life, better education, increased productivity, and economic prosperity if women are educated. The study's goal is to investigate parents' attitudes toward the education of girl children in rural areas, as well as to determine the parents' educational and cultural backgrounds, as well as to assess the various factors that influence parents' attitudes toward girl child education, and the social impact. The investigation is carried out with the goal of using just analytical data as a final result. The data was gathered through a questionnaire, with a sample size of 100 people drawn from rural areas of Villupuram district, Tamil Nadu. SPSS was used to review and analyze the data that had been collected. As a result of this study's findings, the study has concentrated on the social advancement strategy and how parents view their children's schooling.

Keywords: Education, Girl Children, Parent Attitude, Villupuram District, Tamil Nadu.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a significant driver of development and one of the most effective tools for eliminating poverty, gender inequality, peace, and stability. The majority of children in the globe today attend primary school, thanks to great progress made by developing countries in bringing children into classrooms.

"Every year, so much money is spent on war machines," said King Martin Luther four centuries ago.

Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru once famously said that "if you educate a man you educate an individual, however, if you educate a woman you educate a whole family." it will be a dream

of any nation to march towards progress and prosperity, it will not be fulfilled until women actively participate in all development activities, so today there is a huge task to deal with education.

“Education is the most powerful weapon which you can use to change the world,” as said by Nelson Mandela.

The Kothari Commission stated. "Women's education is more important than men's education for the full development of our human resources, for home improvement, and for shaping the children's character in the most impressive years of childhood."

Education is to train children for day-to-day living, which include enabling them to care for the need of the family and relations as well as the nation. A successful and grateful education should also foster in children they enjoy and happiness of living and to help them to take their place in the society as well as balanced individuals.

Schooling is vital to everybody. Schooling isn't just the right of male yet female too. Without teaching the female of the country we can't expect a created country. Female assumes a crucial part in the overall advancement of a country. If we have any desire to make a majority rules system fruitful, female should be instructed. They are the real developers of blissful homes. Why not put more in the dynamic and brilliant ladies of our country who are equipped for educating and supporting our youngsters? "Young ladies" training is impacted in numerous areas in light of the absence of offices like schools in provincial regions, schools showed by male educators of co-training, distance from schools. Guardians would rather not send their little girls to a school found five/six kilometers away. Such a film recognizes ladies from Western and Indian practices. What they are truly arranging is a revolting picture of instructed ladies, hence making disdain over schooling. There is a should try to understand the significance of film in persuading individuals to get schooling and purging the obliviousness among them.

IMPORTANCE OF GIRL CHILD EDUCATION

Raising young ladies' instructive levels exhibits the positive effect that schooling might have on their wellbeing and monetary possibilities, as well as making opportunities for their whole local area. Kids whose mothers have accomplished grade school have a half lower infant death rate than youngsters whose moms are uneducated. On the planet's most unfortunate nations, a big part, everything being equal, don't finish optional school. As per review, each extra year of school for young ladies helps their future by 15%. Ladies put a greater amount of their pay in their families than guys, subsequently reassuring female training works on their financial potential and thus their youngsters' personal satisfaction.

Putting resources into ladies' schooling significantly affects networks, countries, and the whole planet. Ladies who are taught are less inclined to wed youthful guys and are bound to have a better, more useful life. Training for young ladies produces both economy and disparity. It serves to a lot more secure, more grounded local area by permitting everybody, including young men and young ladies, to accomplish their maximum capacity. Nonetheless, training for young ladies involves something other than going to class. To forestall being over-addressed,

young ladies have a good sense of reassurance and certain about the homeroom and take part in the courses and callings fitting their personal preference. Ladies who are accomplished can settle on all around informed choices in light of the best prospects that anyone could hope to find.

Since guaranteeing young ladies auxiliary schooling and acquire the information and abilities required forever and work is one of the best improvement measures. Young ladies and young men both have equivalent admittance to tutoring. Young ladies' schooling saves lives and assists families, networks and economies with thriving. A country's efficiency rises and financial development is invigorated when its female populace is instructed.

ESSENTIAL ROLE OF PARENTS

As recently expressed, training is the country's practice and guardians ought to pass down to their youngsters to grow up to be independent, scholarly, and useful citizenry. The uninformed guardians are work for long length in their work environments as their youngsters get the best schooling in their homerooms and conceivable later on. Accordingly, we might reason that schooling assumes a significant part in the improvement of the countries, especially free and general training for both male and female adolescents. Considering the above instructive objectives, as well as numerous others, it is both captivating and troubling to discover that guardians in country regions don't esteem young lady kid schooling.

PROBLEMS OF GIRL CHILDRENS EDUCATION

The young lady kid is oppressed because of necessities like cleaning and training. The child young lady is fragile and needs a ton of care. Guardians likewise believe that they need to burn through huge load of cash on their schooling and school and marriage. The venture can thusly recommend that the guardians of the neighborhood government figure out the explanations behind the guardians' demeanor towards young lady kid schooling and keep on resolving the issue in the territory of Tamil Nadu. Young lady kid instruction is a far reaching term of a perplexing arrangement of issues and incorporates neighborhood schooling, essential training, optional schooling, wellbeing instruction and tertiary training explicitly examined for young ladies and ladies. This is generally alluded to as female schooling or ladies' schooling. This incorporates regions like orientation uniformity and admittance to schooling. A significant connection to lighten the instructive neediness of ladies and young ladies. Disparities in training for female and ladies are mind boggling: ladies and female face straight out hindrances to passage to school, for instance, viciousness against ladies or limitations of young ladies from going to class, while different issues are more precise and less absolute, for instance, science, innovation, designing, arithmetic instruction lopsidedness are well established, even in Europe and North America. In a few Western nations, ladies have beaten men at many degrees of training.

DISADVANTAGES OF GIRL CHILD EDUCATION

This will only be achieved when the most backward women are encouraged to enter and complete pre- and primary education

- (1) Gender preference in having children
- (2) Importance for their education
- (3) Functional pattern in daily life
- (4) Parental approach (a) Menstruation and (b) Girl child after marriage.

Education is the process by which a society transmits the accumulated knowledge skills and values from one generation to another. Education should provide means and opportunities to enhance the child's creative expression and ability to appreciate aesthetics. Education brings knowledge about the world around us. It develops children with the ability to explain things from the right perspective. Education for girls is very valuable regardless of rural environment. In any argument, it was established that girl children should stay out of schools. Women go out, everything is the same. The duration of a woman's education is:

- a. The ability to finance her parents' for education,
- b. The knowledge of the parents about how far a girl can be educated and
- c. Their knowledge of whether there should be a choice is made in good faith to educate a boy over a girl.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To investigate the parents attitude towards the education of girl children in rural area with special reference to Villupuram District, Tamilnadu.
- 2) To find out the parents' education level and their cultural of different level towards education of girl children.
- 3) To determine the factors influence towards education of girl children in view of parents and girls.
- 4) To analyze the income level of the parents and the social impact in view of education of girl children in rural areas.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Anozie, O et al. (2020), concentrates on investigated that the strengthening of young ladies is a precondition for the strengthening of ladies and the foundation of public advancement. The review took a gander at guardians' perspectives on their girls' strengthening needs in rustic families in Nigeria's Oyo state. A sum of 112 family heads from Saki West and Iseyin Local Government Areas were chosen utilizing a multi-stage inspecting method (LGAs). In spite of the way that the greater part of the respondents (53.6%) had a serious level of mindfulness, around 51% had a negative demeanor toward female strengthening. Guardians' mentalities on young lady kid strengthening ought to be improved through grown-up proficiency and

government funded instruction programs, as indicated by this review. As per Ifeoma P Okafor, (2020), it couldn't possibly be more significant the way that significant female training is, especially in unfortunate countries. Ladies' schooling seems to straightforwardly affect a nation's social, monetary, and political prosperity. The review's discoveries uncovered that a few guardians' obliviousness affects young lady kid training, that it is a misuse of cash, and that it isn't beneficial. As per the review's decisions, government organizations like the Ministry of Education, Ministry of Health, and other youth-related foundations ought to have programs made for guardians on young lady kid training, and instructors ought to be utilized at all levels all through the country.

As per **Daud Khan (2019)**, training is a far reaching process through which an individual gets the important information and abilities to empower that person to add to the general public's general development completely. Female grown-ups' instructive fulfillment is a critical calculate their presentation in different regions, including work advancement, keeping up with their own wellbeing, and anticipating the eventual fate of their kids. This article was arranged following an exhaustive examination concerning guardians' perspectives toward their little girls' schooling and their responses when their girls wish to seek after advanced education. This article additionally checks out at the variables that impact the guardians' perspectives.

As per **Jayanthi and others (2019)**, in the territory of Tamil Nadu, an equivalent schooling system was suggested. It was felt that by embracing this schooling system, we would have the option to give equivalent instruction to all younger students no matter what their area, like country or metropolitan, upper or lower position, or religion. After much resistance, obstacles, and vulnerability, this new schooling system was conceived. Assurance and endeavors to lay out another schooling system are basic. Educators', understudies', and guardians' perspectives about another school system influence choices and public advancement. Instructors and guardians share essential obligation regarding their understudies' psychological and actual turn of events. One of the most pivotal parts of a kid's schooling is their disposition. The comprehension of teachers and their inspirational perspectives toward another school system are basic to its fruitful and successful execution. As indicated by Jyoti Gupta (2019), instruction is getting additional consideration from instructors, government authorities, guardians, and the overall population. Just with the opportunity of ladies and the enlivening of the majority would our nation experience genuine development? "Orientation fairness" is a worldwide issue that must be tended to. India is by and large especially hard struck. Individual perspectives and ways of behaving about ladies' status, orientation equity, sex imbalances, work contrasts, and formative worries all impact changes in a country's segment cosmetics. Thus, something is generally off-base, as there are extensively more uninformed ladies in our country because of a similar reason. These issues should be recognized and proper arrangements concocted so all ladies can get instruction.

The significant goals of the exploration, as per **Manimekalai, K (2019)**, are to get close enough to young lady kids' schooling and to examine training's impressive potential, as well as to research financial and social circumstances and to break down guardians' mentalities toward the requirement for young lady's schooling. As per the discoveries of the review, most of

guardians are endeavoring to keep their young lady kids out of center school due to social factors, for example, family work, caring more youthful kin, an absence of female instructors, and the financial medical condition for guardians/kids; early marriage and absence of orientation mindfulness are the most difficult issues for the young lady's schooling.

Nilofer Jan and others (2019), the reason for this study was to decide guardians' impression of young ladies' schooling in the Jahangir Abad locale of Bhopal (MP) in the scholastic year 2016-17. As per the discoveries, most of the females in Jahangir are devastated (43%), with month to month wages going from 5001 to 10000 Rs. Besides, the greatest level of male guardians (37%) were workers, and the most noteworthy level of female guardians (88%) were housewives, with only one government representative among them. Most of male guardians (29%) have optional training, while the minorities (11%) have rudimentary schooling. Essentially, information showed that the greatest level of female guardians (25%) had optional schooling, while the least number (7%), had a post-auxiliary degree.

As per **Sanju Das and others (2019)**, teaching a young lady kid is basic in resolving various cultural issues that ladies face in India. Schooling kills lack of education, yet additionally assists individuals with turning out to be more mindful, capable, and useful. Ladies represent roughly 50% of the populace, making them a significant human asset who assume a significant part in local area improvement and public financial age. "At the point when 10% more young ladies go to class, a country's GDP becomes on normal by 3%," as per the Council on Foreign Relations. In any case, regardless of this, guardians' all's consciousness of their girls' schooling has diminished fundamentally. The Indian government and different state legislatures have delivered different CCT drives to work on young ladies' schooling, yet no massive changes have happened.

Susanne Schwab (2019), all kids in similar homerooms, in similar schools idea wherein youngsters with unique necessities (SEN) enjoy most of their school day with understudies who don't have extraordinary requirements. As per the writing, mentalities toward comprehensive training, as well as view of comprehensive showing practices and assets, are fundamental components in carrying out consideration. These three angles are considered according to the viewpoint of guardians in this exploration. Guardians of kids in comprehensive or typical courses, then again, see no progressions in assets. What's more, relapse research shows that the indicators of guardians' mentalities toward comprehensive training are subject to the sort of debilitation.

As per **Aarti Yadav (2018)**, India's school training is tormented by low learning results, as proven by various public reports. A significant group of examination upholds the connection between the social climate of the homeroom and understudy learning results. This review takes a gander at how educators and understudies feel about the social climate in the study hall on three levels: relationship, self-awareness/objective direction, and framework support and change. The exploration utilized an expressive overview plan. The discoveries demonstrate that educators and understudies have tantamount perspectives on the elements of connection, instructor backing, and assignment direction, suggesting that peer cooperation and instructor support for understudies are lacking in their mental angles.

Alrasheed H. et al. (2018), uncorrected refractive mistake is a main source of preventable visual debilitation, and it can impact individuals' public activities, instructive open doors, and monetary possibilities. Wearing exhibitions could undoubtedly resolve this issue, yet such methodologies are ignored because of certain societies' mentalities and misguided judgments about scene wear and eye care. To decide how Sudanese secondary school understudies and their folks feel about wearing glasses. The examination was completed in eight Sudanese secondary schools that were picked aimlessly. As per the information, 39%, 32%, and 27.1 percent of understudies accept that wearing scenes affects their instructive, business, and conjugal potential outcomes, individually. Wearing exhibitions, as per 36.4 percent of understudies, could debilitate or harm the eyes, driving in early visual impairment, while 22.5 percent thought scenes were exclusively for the older. Females gave off an impression of being more inclined to social and mental uneasiness than guys while wearing displays. Assuming an eye specialist requested exhibitions, 79% of the guardians knew that they would further develop vision. Nonetheless, guardians expressed that wearing exhibitions had mental repercussions, especially among females, and that they brought down visual power. Guardians accepted that their youngsters had lost a fundamental resource, that the local area considered them to be debilitated, and that their kids could become visually impaired from here on out. Dread and shame related with wearing scenes are normal among Sudanese understudies and their folks, particularly among young ladies.

Anna Onoyase (2018) directed a concentrate in Sokoto State, Nigeria, to assess guardians' mentalities about female-youngster optional training. The review was directed by one exploration subject and one speculation. The examination was led as an elucidating study with an ex-post facto plan. The specialist utilized an instrument in light of Tremba and Umaru's (2015) work. "Disposition of Parents toward Female Child Secondary Education Questionnaire" is the name of the apparatus (APTFCSEQ). It was found that there is no significant variety in perspectives about female-kid optional training between guardians in metropolitan and provincial areas. This finding shows that whether or not the parent lives in a metropolitan or country district, they have all expressed an assessment in same course in the review.

The objective of the concentrate by **Hemavathi Dasappa et al., (2018)** was to explore the pervasiveness of weight and overweight among school understudies matured 6 to 13. In a tuition based school in Bangalore city, guardians finished a normalized survey, and a school nurture estimated weight and level. Corpulence was 17.13 percent and overweight was 13.20 percent. The predominance was profoundly connected to birth weight and support in sports. Sports assist youngsters with trying not to become overweight or corpulent. Parental perspectives toward eating feasts with their kids and assessing their youngsters' active work were defensive, while parental mentalities toward directing their youngsters' nourishment were a gamble factor for overweight and stoutness. As per the discoveries, the commonness of overweight and corpulence is ascending in lockstep. Higher birth loads and a parental demeanor of dealing with the eating of their kids are likewise potential gamble factors. Cooperation in sports, parental perspectives toward eating with kids, and attention to their actual work are defensive variables.

As per **Martinez-Ferrer and partners (2018)**, was to explore the connections between kid to-parent animosity and parental socialization strategies, as well as risky utilization of person to person communication locales, alexithymia, and mentalities toward institutional expert in young people. The discoveries uncovered that elevated degrees of kid to-parent savagery were connected to dangerous utilization of long range interpersonal communication locales, alexithymia, and a more uplifting perspective toward normal practice infringement. It was likewise shown that youngsters from liberal families had the least evaluations in hazardous social use.

To dissect this survey, **Manivannan and others (2018)** furnished the specialist with a wide comprehension of the numerous thoughts related to tension in Higher Secondary understudies. It furnished the scientist with a strong premise and opened the way for his examinations. It permitted the scientist to pick the examination instruments she really wanted for this task. The scientist (I) sums up the significant commitments of pertinent examinations and papers to the group of information viable, remembering the presentation's concentration. (ii) Assess the current "cutting edge" for the collection of information viable, featuring key strategic blunders or exploration holes, errors in principle and ends, and regions or subjects that ought to be investigated further. (iii) Finish by expounding on the association between the significant subject of the writing survey and a more extensive area of study, like a discipline, a logical movement, or a vocation.

Alok Gardia and Nitu Kaur (2014), led a review to find out about and grasp guardians' perspectives on tutoring and related school training issues, which have a huge impact in deciding the kind of instruction their kids get. The examination helped with distinguishing urgent areas of parental interest to give top notch schooling to their kids. It helped with recognizing parental worries about educational program content, showing quality and norms, expertise and character advancement, and vocation guiding, in addition to other things. The review's discoveries will help educationalists, educators, and executives in figuring out current parental perspectives toward tutoring and the components that impact their turn of events.

Sandeep Kumar Jaiswal and others (2017) looks at the examination writing on the connection between nurturing practices, for example, nurturing style, parental assumptions, parental home and school inclusion exercises, and understudies' scholastic presentation at the rudimentary and center school levels. Various builds of parental support play a significant impact in different ways, as per experimental review assessments. Nonetheless, a few investigations show that parental interest diminishes as youngster's progress through center and secondary school. Besides, the investigation discovered that definitive nurturing style is connected to worked on scholastic accomplishment at all degrees of schooling, though this relationship isn't uniform across nationality, culture, or financial class. With some variety, parental contribution at home and at school has additionally been connected to work on scholastic achievement. Nonetheless, when contrasted with different kinds of parental cooperation, parental assumptions for their youngster's instructive accomplishment greatest affected scholarly execution.

H. Willaby and others (2017), regardless of the way that immunization reluctance is a general wellbeing concern, the review's experience and points are as per the following. The objectives of this study were to make sense of Australian guardians' perspectives, activities, and stresses over inoculation, distinguish qualities connected to antibody rebelliousness, and deal general experts with immunization data (GPs). GPs assume a basic part in tending to immunization concerns. Guardians' getting it and confidence in immunization will work on because of training and contact with them, bringing about expanded antibody consistence.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study deals with both primary and secondary data. The primary data was collected by convenient sampling techniques if adopted for the study. The Secondary data required for the study was from books, magazines, journals, newspaper, past research, reports and various records. The sample size of the study is limited to 100 and due to the constraint of time the study is limited only to rural areas in Villupuram district. The nature of respondents were hesitant answer certain questions.

DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

I. The below table composed from the various secondary data about the education and literacy level of Villupuram District, Tamilnadu.

Table -1

Year	1991	2001	2011
Male	60.9	75.5	80.58
Female	35.4	52.5	63.51
TOTAL	48.4	64.7	72.08

Source: Villupuram District at a glance

The census ratio variation on education and literacy in Villupuram district is shown in table 1.1. The district's literacy rate is 72.08 percent, according to the 2011 census. The district has the largest gender disparity (17%), with men having an 81 percent literacy rate and women having a 64 percent literacy rate. From 2001 onwards, however, we can see an improvement in both the general literacy rate and the gender gap. Table 1.1 shows the literacy rate and the gender disparity by volume. The literacy rate of constituencies like Koliyanur, Villupuram, and Marakkanam is much higher than the district average, as shown in the table (72 per cent). Gender gap is higher in Koliyanur (21 per cent) and Vanurthan 20 per cent. This is the lowest in Villupuram constituency (1.14 per cent) in the district.

II. The below table composed from various secondary data about the Gender and Number of primary school in Villupuram District, Tamilnadu.

Table-2

S. No	Details	Villupuram
1	Gender wise population	
	Boys	1.98 lakhs
	Girls	1.91 lakhs
	Total	3.89 lakhs
2	Total no.of primary schools	
	Rural	1964
	Urban	40
	Total	2004

Source: Villupuram District at a glance

The census ratios for Gender and Number of Primary Schools in Villupuram District are shown in Table 1.2. According to the 2011 census, there are 1.98 lakh boys and 1.91 lakh girls in elementary, intermediate, and higher secondary schools. In addition, there are 1964 elementary schools in Villupuram District's rural areas, with 40 schools in the metropolitan zone. It reveals that secondary and senior secondary schools are scarce in Tamil Nadu's Villupuram District.

III. The below details are composed from various secondary data about the school Education on drop out data of girl children in Villupuram District, Tamilnadu.

Parents were asked about the importance of girl child education. The majority of parents felt that education was important so that they could command respect from the female community, learn to read and write, and find respectable jobs in the future.

Chennai: The Sarva Siksha Abhiyan (SSA) survey said that 37,488 children were expelled from schools across the state at the beginning of this academic year in June. Villupuram district has the highest number of dropouts. Villupuram district tops the list with 2,472 students, followed by Coimbatore with 2,203 students and Krishnagiri with 2,073 students. There are 1,821 students in schools in Chennai district. "Many people here are migrating to other districts and states in search of work. When they leave their place, they take their children with them. After months of work, their children drop out of school," said SSA officials in the district. "Ordinary laborers below the poverty line usually work in brick kiln rooms in Tiruvallur and other districts and they migrate to Kerala and cut down trees. Therefore, the number of school children in the district is more or less every year".

Due to the migration of labor from outside the state, this number will increase after June and the workers for the brick kiln rooms will be coming from outside the states only in December 2019-20. In Chennai district too, the number is slightly higher. In the Rayapuram region alone, more than 400 children are out of school. “All students were enrolled in schools. They left because of the economic background of their families,” said a Chennai district education official.

IV. By using the primary data the below table shows the Percentage wise Socio-demographic details of the respondents

Table -3

S. No	Socio demographic details of the respondents	Percentage
Gender	Male	46 %
	Female	54 %
Age	18 - 20	7 %
	20 - 30	30 %
	30 - 40	45 %
	40 and Above	18 %
	10 th	26 %
Educational Qualification	12 th	19 %
	UG	8 %
	PG	4 %
	Uneducated	43 %
	Daily Worker	38 %
Occupation	Farmer	41 %
	Government Employee	10 %
	Private Employee	10 %
	Business	1 %
	Less than 10,000	60 %
Monthly Income	10,000 to 20,000	30 %
	30,000 to 40,000	9 %
	More Than 40,000	1 %
	1 to 3 members	18 %
Family Members	4 and Above	50 %
	More Than 5	32 %
	1	18 %
Children in their Family	2	56 %
	3	26 %
	1	63 %
Girl child in their Family	2	32 %
	3	5 %

SOURCE: Primary data

Socio demographic details of the Respondents

One way ANOVA

Table 4- ANOVA

Factors		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Girls Education is Essential for the Society	Between Groups	1.227	1	1.227	10.607	.002
	Within Groups	11.333	98	.116		
	Total	12.560	99			
Girls education contributes to economy of the country in the long run	Between Groups	12.301	1	12.301	41.200	.000
	Within Groups	29.259	98	.299		
	Total	41.560	99			
Do equal opportunities is provided to girls in education	Between Groups	12.301	1	12.301	69.845	.000
	Within Groups	17.259	98	.176		
	Total	29.560	99			
The lack of parental education affect the girl's education	Between Groups	149.406	1	149.406	199.062	.000
	Within Groups	73.554	98	.751		
	Total	222.960	99			
Parents income affect girls' education	Between Groups	155.550	1	155.550	240.859	.000
	Within Groups	63.290	98	.646		
	Total	218.840	99			
It is not appropriate for girls to be educated according to our tamil culture and traditions	Between Groups	128.877	1	128.877	76.622	.000
	Within Groups	164.833	98	1.682		
	Total	293.710	99			
It is not right to send girls to school as they will be in the same environment with the boys	Between Groups	152.264	1	152.264	238.806	.000
	Within Groups	62.486	98	.638		
	Total	214.750	99			
It is morally wrong to send girls above certain age to school	Between Groups	146.769	1	146.769	166.975	.000
	Within Groups	86.141	98	.879		
	Total	232.910	99			
It is not appropriate for girls to go another place for education	Between Groups	124.809	1	124.809	170.946	.000
	Within Groups	71.551	98	.730		
	Total	196.360	99			

The value of F of the given factors are 10.60, 41.20, 69.84, 199.06, 76.62, 238.80, 166.97 and 170.94 which reaches significance with a p-value of .002 & .000 for all the factors (which is less than the .05 alpha level). This means there is a statistically significant difference between the means of the different levels of the Girls education variable.

Paired Sample t-Test

H₀ - There is a significant relationship between Gender and to equal education for son and daughter, to educate your daughter and sending girls for education.

H₁ - There is no significant relationship between Gender and equal education son and daughter, to educate your daughter and sending girls for education

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Gender & Allow your son and daughter to receive an equal education	100	.188	.060
Pair 2	Gender & Agree to educate your daughter	100	.212	.034
Pair 3	Gender & Rural parents are sending girls for education	100	.495	.000

Factors		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Gender - Allow your son and daughter to receive an equal education	.50000	.50252	.05025	.40029	.59971	9.950	99	.000
Pair 2	Gender - Agree to educate your daughter	.49000	.50242	.05024	.39031	.58969	9.753	99	.000
Pair 3	Gender - Rural parents are sending girls for education	.23000	.54781	.05478	.12130	.33870	4.198	99	.000

The above paired samples t test shows the t value as 9.950, 9.753 & 4.198 which gives us a p-value – or 2-tailed significance value – of .000. A standard alpha level is .05, and .000 is smaller than .05, so through this study we are able to reject the null hypothesis which asserts there is no significant difference between the Gender and other three variables.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This research has demonstrated the parents' attitudes on the education of their daughters, as well as the elements that influence their education. The main findings and consequences are that (43 percent) of the population has illiterate (non-educated) parents. According to the

findings, the majority of respondent's parents (89 percent) believe that girls' education is critical for society.

Our culture is evolving in the contemporary period, and rural households must recognize the need of both boys and girls education in order to enhance all aspects of society. Knowledge is required for all muscularity; therefore, all rural parents should ensure that their children are educated and have a proper path to school without regard to gender.

SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The review's general positive assessment of their girls' schooling among rustic guardians proposes that the public authority's endeavors to further develop general instruction have been effective. Better work prospects and pay creation plans would go quite far toward advancing the monetary circumstance of rustic families, thus upgrading their uplifting outlook and interest in organizing advanced education for their girls. Guardians should explain how they might interpret the point of their girls' schooling. Guardians ought to anticipate that their little girls should keep on learning since, supposing that they take a stab at significance, achievement will follow.

Guardians regularly accept that their little girls are unequipped for going with sound work choices. Be that as it may, no parental commitment to the work decision is required. Permit females to settle on their own choices in view of their inclinations, shortcomings, and abilities. Guardians ought to sustain their little girls' pioneering soul. The objective of instruction ought to never be to find a new line of work; rather, it ought to be to turn into a decent individual who is confident and adds to society.

It is additionally suggested that foundation heads and legislators foster systems to increment family association in schooling to impact guardians' mentalities toward their girls' advanced education. It was likewise suggested that the service of instruction utilize these discoveries to teach instructors about the significance of a positive parental disposition toward training and how it helps every relative's kid.

CONCLUSION

The inquirer information indicate that the country bunches were found for the young lady kids instruction. They accepted higher investigations would empower their young lady kids to have better pay and that tutoring isn't adequate. There are numerous social biases, social traditions, and standards which tension access of ladies to schooling overall and advanced education. The deep rooted traditions and various convictions, for example, the retirement and ladies, universe of lady as not the same as men, ladies at last getting hitched and disappointment of venture on their schooling.

Country bunches were found for the training of young lady adolescents, as per the inquirer information. They accepted that more noteworthy instruction would assist their young lady kids with bringing in additional cash and that tutoring alone wouldn't get the job done. Numerous social biases, shows, and standards hinder ladies' admittance to training overall and

advanced education specifically. Old propensities and perspectives about retirement and ladies, the universe of ladies as unmistakable from that of men, ladies at long last wedding, and the failure to put resources into their schooling. These are critical elements in the demeanor of guardians, especially uninformed guardians, close to the training of ladies, yet in this review, we are examining the schooling of young lady kids, and the majority of the young ladies have a place with a center societal position in the public eye regarding their folks' pay, as the political, social, monetary, and primary factors that limit young ladies' schooling are researched.

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